

EFFECTS OF CHRONIC ENDOMETRITIS ON REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH IN
WOMEN, MODERN INTERPRETATION

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Meaning: The cells that make up the endometrium are hormonally dependent and change depending on the phase of the menstrual cycle. The endometrium itself consists of two layers, the first of which is functional and consists of cells that change during the cycle and are rejected with each menstruation.

Aims and objectives of the study: Here the embryo must be attached after transfer. But the mucous membrane damaged by inflammation may not accept the attempts of the embryo. The main cause of endometritis is inflammatory diseases. Usually, the uterine cavity is sterile, i.e. it is completely free of microorganisms. However, if an inflammatory process develops in the vagina, often caused by sexually transmitted infections, then these microorganisms enter the uterine cavity, and then the fallopian tubes and abdominal cavity, causing inflammation. It can cause the process of aging.

Research materials and methods: Inflammation is a universal protective reaction of the body. Its results are the activation of the immune system aimed at suppressing and destroying the microbe. However, in the tissues, often after inflammation, a dense connective tissue is formed, which leads to a violation of the blood supply to the tissues. One of the most unpleasant moments is that the inflammatory process can go from an acute stage to a chronic stage.

Research results: Often the infection becomes a chronic condition - a "dormant" condition. And it can increase due to adverse environmental factors or general health, with the development of immunodeficiency conditions, including during the IVF program and subsequent pregnancy. With the help of ultrasound, the disease can be detected - the mucous membrane of the uterus changes, thickens in places, and the presence of fluid in the cavity is visible. In addition, a hysteroscopy is performed - an examination of the uterine cavity, in which changes in the mucous membrane are visible. At the same time, the presence of chronic endometritis can be confirmed or rejected only by histological examination.

Conclusions: If after treatment there are no consequences in the form of scars on the uterine lining, then the probability of conception increases significantly. After treatment, a woman can get pregnant after about 2-4 cycles. At the same time, it is necessary to continue to support the normal

state of the body, the natural flora of the vagina and the woman's immunity. It is recommended to carry out this support in the first 3 months of pregnancy. During IVF, chronic endometritis manifests itself in the absence of pregnancy after transplantation of high-grade embryos: they simply have nothing to attach to, the changed mucous membrane rejects them. Therefore, research is required to identify endometritis and treat the disease. This increases the probability of success of the IVF program.

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